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SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF CRANIODORSAL COXOFEMORAL LUXATION IN A DOG USING A NEW UHMWPE IMPLANT

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Introduction:

Coxofemoral luxation (CFL) accounts for 90% of cases of joint luxation in dogs, mainly caused by trauma. Current treatment recommendations include extra- or intra-articular stabilization of the hip joint by iliofemoral suture or various synthetic implants, generally using toggle pins for acetabular fixation.

Objectives:

Treat an 8-year-old male bearded collie who was referred for left traumatic CFL subsequent to a dog fight.

Methods:

The orthopedic examination of the CF joint revealed pain and cracking, and a dorsal displacement of the greater trochanter. X-rays confirmed the diagnosis and discreet osteoarthritis was observed. Surgical treatment was performed by primary ligament repair, followed by the insertion of an UHMWPE implant which was pre-assembled with a cortical button and implanted with an interference screw for the intra-articular reconstruction of the round ligament. Immediate postoperative X-rays showed that the implantation of the interference screw followed the drilling axis.

Results:

The dog started using the operated hindlimb one day postoperatively. At four weeks postoperatively, orthopedic examination showed no lameness nor pain during mobilization, nor loss of joint mobility in the contralateral hindlimb. 4-week postoperative X-rays showed perfect coaptation of the operated coxofemoral joint.

Conclusions:

Reconstruction of the round ligament using an UHMWPE implant fixed by an acetabular cortical button and a femoral interference screw was an early success in this case report, as shown by postoperative X-rays and orthopedic control. However, owing to the short postoperative follow-up period, this result needs to be confirmed. A prospective study has already been launched to validate or refute these encouraging findings.